

////////////////////////////////////

USING DIY CARTOON STORYBOARDS, LIVE SKETCHING AND CO-SKETCHING TO INVOLVE YOUNG AND OLDER USERS IN PARTICIPATORY DESIGN

Robb Mitchell
SPIRE Centre, University of Southern
Denmark

Mie Nørgaard
The IT University of Copenhagen,
Denmark

robb@telecosy.com

mienoergaard@itu.dk

ABSTRACT

This paper presents and discusses results from two cases, where various sketching techniques including DIY cartoon storyboards, live sketching and co-sketching, were used to provoke young and older users to think about new designs and design qualities, and to help designers evaluate and investigate these ideas together with users. Results suggest that both amateur and expert sketching can provoke and support valuable evaluation and generation of design concepts. We conclude with presenting recommendations for the use of sketching activities in participatory design.

Keywords: Sketching techniques, participatory design, co-design, facilitation.

INTRODUCTION

Anyone who has ever facilitated a participatory design session knows that certain groups of users prove difficult to engage in such work. Some people are so result-oriented that discussions become more technical and practical than inspiring or new. Others are confused by fuzzy talk on possible future technologies and find it hard or intimidating to make comments or suggestions. These are perhaps very normal restrictions that at times apply to most of us. Certain users have even greater difficulties in participating in participatory design exercises. Those users include people with limited abilities for articulating ideas such as people with mental handicaps, reduced language skills or drug and alcohol abuse related impairments.

Over the last five years, we have facilitated various workshops involving users with cognitive impairments. This work includes supporting users with mental handicaps in co-design activities related to the design of services and physical living environments, and supporting people with drug and alcohol-related impairments in discussions related to the special use situations faced by homeless people suffering from abuse or mental problems. Here, the use of a technique called extreme sketching (Nørgaard, 2011), a technique related to graphic recording and graphic facilitation (Valenza and Adkins, 2009), has been successfully deployed to aid reflection and discussion since such users prove difficult to engage in a more traditional interview setting, and are hard to involve in brainstorm activities that demand focus and attention for a longer period of time (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Examples of extreme sketches that documents and twists insights from a plenum discussion by adding provocation and satire

Figure 2. Scenes from a two-day innovation camp on creating 100 designs and services for socially excluded groups. Photo: Tine Harden

Figure 3. co-design workshop on living environments and service designs for people with cognitive disabilities

Our experiences have shown how such sketching activities can help create a situation where users feel comfortable engaging with both the professional sketcher and the sketches, and can easily do so (Figures 2 & 3). The result of using low-tech paper sketches as the turning point for interaction and conversation is an informal and relaxed interview setting that benefits from sketching being an activity, which the partakers can do side by side, alone or together, and which is easy to join or leave at will. Our past experiences have shown that the sketches serve as bi-directional tickets to talk (Sacks, 1992) in that users often approach the professional sketcher with questions about the sketches and comments about how a situation might look in their everyday life, and that the professional sketcher uses the sketches to ask the participant questions related to design preferences and living situation. These experiences have inspired the authors to write this paper, in which we argue how thinking in terms of using paper sketching as a ticket to talk can benefit collaboration with other user groups that often prove difficult to involve in discussions on design, such as children and older adults.

We present two cases where we deploy various sketching techniques, including DIY cartoon storyboards, live sketching, and co-sketching to explore how designers might benefit from exploring concepts and designs by using sketching techniques to facilitate participatory design sessions with children and older adults.

RELATED WORK

In the design community, sketching is often understood as the production of early paper sketches (Goldsmidt, 1991, 2003), which are used by architects and others who explore the form and function of things. But not all design activities relate to form and function, and designers might also include sketching techniques as a means to drive discussion and thinking when working together with users, which is the aim of most participatory design sessions.

Buxton (2007) uses the term sketch to describe any representation of an idea or concept that is evocative and can be used to get new ideas, develop old ones or think about well-known issues in a new fashion. In Buxton's work the material used to sketch is of little importance as long as the sketches are rapidly made, provoke new questions, and provide the possibility to explore design assumptions quickly and at a low cost. No matter the material qualities of the individual sketches, the act of sketching is thus understood as a tool for aiding idea generation and exploration of ideas in a design situation. This goes for professional designers and amateurs alike. Apart from helping new thinking, sketching also serve to help designers talk and about and share an idea, as well as remember and store its key components (Ferguson, 1992, McGown & Green, 1998, Ullman, Wood, & Craig, 1990) which is why sketching is many designers' preferred technique to inspire thinking and help them communicate with others. When used together with users and other non-specialists the value of low-tech sketches might be understood as tickets to talk (Sacks, 1992), that is, as an invitation to engage in conversation and a natural starting point for such interactions. This is what we explore in this paper.

USING SKETCHING TECHNIQUES TO AID PARTICIPATORY DESIGN

In the following, we present two studies focusing on deploying sketching techniques in participatory design activities with young children and older adults. The cases and the preliminary results are presented in turn below and discussed in detail in the following section.

CASE ONE: CO-CREATED DIY CARTOON STORYBOARDS IN KINDERGARTEN

Figure 4. From case one. The DIY cartoon storyboard with the last frame left blank for the children to complete.

In the first study, children aged 6-8 years were provided with an incomplete hand drawn scenario. (Figure 4). The approach in this case was inspired by participatory design work done by Microsoft which used a professional comic book artist to put children's words into pictures (Moraveji et al, 2007). By contrast the children here were invited to complete the hand drawn scenario by drawing an idea for a concept in the final frame themselves. The crudely drawn comic told the following story: A 7 year old girl has two parents who are very keen on saving energy, but her younger brother is too young to understand this and participate in the family's energy saving

activities (figure 1). To help her parents engage the little brother the girl persuades the inventor's neighbour to invent something that combines play and energy saving. The inventor does not know anything about children's toys, so he asks the girl to describe a playful energy saving device that he could create. The final frame in the DIY cartoon storyboard is left blank with an invitation to the reader to answer this request by drawing a suggestion for a design that combines play and energy saving. For more details, see (Mitchell, 2011).

Figure 5. From case one. Example of a child's response to the DIY cartoon storyboard: glasses that beep and flash if too much power is consumed

Observations from case one

The experiment with the children showed that not only did the sketching exercise using DIY cartoon storyboards help them produce ideas of high quality and range (e.g. Figures 5 and 6), but the children's sketches played an unexpected positive role in motivating design team members, who greatly valued the ambiguity of the children's sketches and ideas.

Figure 6. From case one. Another design concept elicited from a child via the DIY cartoon storyboard: A robot that appears happy or sad, depending upon whether energy is wasted

Figure 7. From case two. Example of a crude DIY cartoon storyboard depicting the design presented in Portocarrero, Cranor, & Bove, (2011)

Figure 8. From case two. The crude DIY cartoon storyboards depicting various design concepts were available on the workshop table for participants to browse as discussions progressed.

CASE TWO: SKETCHES AS RESPONSES TO EMBEDDED INTERFACE RESEARCH

Our second case looks at two activities from a design session with adults aged 63 to 70. Both activities commenced with participants receiving a presentation of three provocative design concepts developed by international researchers, and published at the most recent edition of a leading academic conference concerning tangible and embedded interfaces. The designs were all intended for applications in domestic settings, and were communicated to participants in the form of simple crude cartoons of three to seven frames of drawings (Figures 7 - 9).

Sketching technique 1: Professional Extreme Sketching

Using simple crude cartoons the first activity began with the presentation of concepts for an anthropomorphic central heating controller (Yun & Gross, 2011), a remote piano tutoring system (Xiao & Ishii, 2011) and a drapable textile interface

(Lepinski & Vertegaal, 2011). Each design was discussed in plenum in terms of utility, relevance, and how it might be modified to fit into the users' lives. This discussion was facilitated by a moderator with design background and real time illustrated by a professional visual facilitator using graphic recording and extreme sketching techniques, see Figure 10.

Figure 9. From case two. A participant using enactment and a DIY cartoon storyboard to explain an envisaged application for the presented design concept of an intelligent drapable cloth (Lepinski and Vertegaal, 2011)

Figure 10. From case two. The 3.5 m long frieze created by a professional visual facilitator to support the discussion with the older adults.

Sketching technique 2: Storyboards made by participants

In the next activity, three more inventions for domestic use were presented in the simple cartoon format; A robotic flower pot pet (Kawakami, Tsukada, Kambara, & Siio, 2011), a dream capturing pillow (Portocarrero, Cranor, & Bove, 2011), and a simple communication system using co-located mirrors (Schmeer & Baffi, 2011). Participants were then instructed to visualize how one of those designs might look in their everyday life situation. The format for their visualization was a template with eight empty cartoon frames. The fabricated cartoon storyboards were then presented in plenum, handed over to another participant, who was requested to roughly sketch an ending to the cartoon, (see Figures 11 - 12), and finally presented and explained the storyboard in plenum once again.

Observations from Case Two

The observations and experiences from the two exercises with older adults touch on the usefulness of even simple crude cartoons as a means for explaining and evaluating concepts, which can be difficult to comprehend, the value of including slightly provocative sketches to spur discussion and reflection, and the possibility to use participant generated cartoons to learn about new application domains and to challenge basic design assumptions. Despite not finding any of the designs discussed in the session particularly useful, participants were pleased with the format in which they were communicated. The crude cartoon storyboards were successful in communicating the main idea and context of a design, though not so much the motivation for using it. In this respect, participants were very quick to challenge for example the usefulness of using steamy mirrors as a tool for communication.

Figure 11. From case two. Example of a storyboard created by participants. A second participant has elaborated on the storyboard by adding the last three frames.

At the same time, the cartoons did not seem to help participants think of any new angles on a product, in fact they were quick to evaluate something as a failure or a success based on the one example provided by the cartoon.

Figure 12. From case two. Participants drawing to complete DIY cartoon storyboards begun by other participants

Having a discussion visualized by a live sketcher was commented upon as being a feature that participants appreciated, but in terms of utility or success with pushing forward the thinking in new directions, the technique was less successful. The parts of the sketch that had an extreme or provocative edge, such as a naked person in a picture frame as an interface that suggests that a room is very hot, did cause laughs and other ideas, for example that an interface might also show a progressing striptease video according to room temperature. New ideas did not seem triggered in abundance by the live sketching, however, and the use of live sketching would most likely benefit from boosting the extreme sketches by proposing new provocative angles on what is discussed rather than simply documenting what new ideas might come up in the discussion, such as is done in graphic recording.

The exercise where participants should generate their own cartoon storyboards was initially not well received. Participants were reluctant to start sketching and complained that they did not know how to draw or how to make a scenario that was different from the pre-made cartoons shown in the beginning of the session. While most of the storyboards created during this exercise were fairly superficial and avoided details on for

example interaction design, some storyboards did provide the possibility to explore new use contexts and criticize design assumptions. Mostly, however, the storyboards seemed useful as a concrete point of departure for asking participants questions such as “what actions take place between frame three and four?” and “could you imagine another result of the action in frame two?”

DISCUSSION

In the following, we discuss our results with using various sketching techniques with children and older adults in participatory design situations. We specifically look at aspects of our practice related to how the different ages of the user groups affected how they worked, and which benefits and weaknesses with the techniques we observed in the two cases.

AGE AND DIY CARTOON STORYBOARD TECHNIQUE

Not surprisingly, the children in case one were much happier with having to draw cartoon storyboards than the older adults of case two. Initially, the older adults found it very hard to get started and spent substantial time just staring at the empty frames of the cartoon storyboard template. In both the amateur and expertly sketched sessions, however, the older adults were able to consider a much broader range of users, stakeholders and use scenarios than the children were.

BENEFITS OF SKETCHING ACTIVITIES

In comparing the findings from the two sessions, we argue that the use of sketches and sketching as an aid to help users verbalize thoughts and ideas is highly useful in design. Not only for users with cognitive disabilities or other handicaps that make it hard for them to engage in concentrated design discussions, as reported in the beginning of the paper, but for other user groups as well.

In the session with the older adults, the sketching activities as well as the physical sketches served as an effective ticket to talk. The sketching activities, which were very unfamiliar to the participants, caused—after initial getting used to—both smiles and laughs, and helped instigate

questions and explanations about certain uses or use situations for the designs in question. One participant for example, sketched a cartoon storyboard of a completely new use situation for the Touch Trace Mirrors (Schmeer & Baffi, 2011) and a use, which was quite different from what the designers had envisioned. Such a storyboard could serve as valuable input to a discussion on the utility of the proposed design, and the consequences of changing it.

In both studies the designers and moderators were particularly pleased with being able to use sketches as a concrete point of departure for exploring ideas with users, and the sketches' ability to facilitate discussion and reflection, but also recollection of a concept that was discussed earlier. Both the expert sketches and those of the less skilled participants were valued in this respect, which suggest that even fairly crude sketches or incomplete cartoon storyboards are useful as aids to the memory.

The older adults reported that making and viewing sketches was an unfamiliar way of thinking, and that it forced them to consider aspects of their experiences that they might otherwise overlook, such as how a design was placed in a certain physical or social context or how they might interact with it.

WEAKNESSES OF SKETCHING ACTIVITIES

Both groups of users from case one and two sketched about and talked about what interested them, not what they were asked to do (although elicitation of "real interests" could in be argued to be a strength). Based on this observation, we conclude that providing visual materials and activities does not remove the need for skilful and assertive facilitation, perhaps quite the reverse, considering the lively atmosphere during both participatory sessions. Actually, the provocations of working with sketches seemed to have effect of enlivening participants more than many other participatory design techniques that the authors have worked with.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTITIONERS

Below, we sum up our experiences into

recommendations to guide practitioners when considering using paper sketching techniques as an aid to participatory design sessions:

- Ascertain in advance the interests of participants and be prepared to deal with participants who ignore instructions and exercises,
- Topics for exploration with private consumers (as opposed to users from business) should not only have potential relevance to participants' lives, but should be something that affects them greatly,
- Ascertain in advance (or early in a session) the expertise level of participants in relation to target subject matters,
- Smaller groups of participants will help facilitators investigate ideas more closely with participants,
- Smaller groups will also help facilitators keep users on track, since participants seem mostly interested in discussing their own ideas and less interested in listening to those of others.
- DIY cartoon storyboards are very useful as an interview tool, since they allow for questions like "what happens next?", "what happens between these two frames?", and "could the actions in frame three lead to other outcomes than the one shown?"
- Extreme sketching appears more useful to drive discussions when there is a need to build shared social responses from a group of participants, whereas the quiet, solo activity of DIY cartoon storyboarding supports more individual contemplation.
- Extreme sketching seems to help discussions along better than simply recording the discussion using graphic facilitation (Valenza & Adkins 2009). The advice to the sketcher is to suggest new ways for the discussion using very provocative drawings/interpretations in order to help participants think in new ways about a certain design and its potential.

FURTHER WORK

In this paper, we have reported on a relatively

small number of cases and activities. To ensure more insights and greater confidence in the suggested guidelines, more sketching sessions with both different and similar participants, inputs and activities are needed. Follow up interviews with participants from co-sketching exercises could be useful for evaluating a number of aspects of this practice, not least how well the hand drawn sketches function as carriers of memory. Investigating how third parties not present at a sketching session may later interpret the sketches of both experts and amateurs may also uncover additional advantages and disadvantages as to the utility of these methods.

CONCLUSION

We have described and compared several sketching activities involving children and older adults and presented recommendations for design practitioners interested in using such techniques as an aid in participatory design sessions.

Sketching appears to have great potential as a tool for supporting user participation in design but care needs to be taken when selecting appropriate activities and facilitating discussions, which can easily digress because of the lively atmosphere caused by the playfulness of the techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to the participants in both studies, Eckersberg Friskole, Ken Mathiasen, SydEnergi, (case one) and Dansk Fitness, (case two) project partner in the Lev Vel/No Age project, funded by The Danish Council for Technology and Innovation and The Capital Region of Denmark.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Buxton, B. (2007). *Sketching User Experiences - Getting the Design Right and the Right Design*. San Fransisco: Morgan Kaufmann.
- Ferguson, E. S. (1992). *Engineering and the mind's eye*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Goldsmidt, G. (2003). The Backtalk of Self-generated Sketches. *Design Issues* , 19 (1), 72-88.
- Goldsmidt, G. (1991). The Dialectics of Sketching. *Creativity Research Journal* , 4 (2), 123-143.
- Kawakami, A., Tsukada, K., Kambara, K., & Siio, I. (2011). PotPet: Pet-like Flowerpot Robot . *TEI '11: Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. Funchal, Portugal.
- Lepinski, J., & Vertegaal, R. (2011). Cloth Displays: Interacting with Drapable Textile Screens . *TEI '11: Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. Funchal, Portugal.
- Mitchell, R., (2011). Scaffolding Co-Design with An Amateur Quality Comic. *NORDES 11 - Nordic Design Research Conference*. Helsinki, Finland.
- McGown, A., & Green, G. (1998). Visible ideas, informational patterns of conceptual sketch activity. *Design studies* , 19, 431-453.
- Moraveji, N., Ding , J. Li, J., O'Kelley, P. and Woolf, S. (2007) Comicboarding: using comics as proxies for participatory design with children, *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems*, pp. 1371-1374.
- Nørgaard, M. (2011). Using extreme sketching to help reflections on business. *PINC Participatory Innovation Conference 2011*, (pp. 341-345). Sønderborg.
- Portocarrero, E., Cranor, D., & Bove, M. (2011). Pillow-Jar: Seamless interface for Dream Priming, Recalling and Playback . *TEI '11: Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. Funchal, Portugal.
- Sacks, H. (1992). *Lectures on Conversation*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Schmeer, J., & Baffi, T. (2011). Touch Trace Mirror: Asynchronous, Collaborative Messaging as a Concept for Creating a Relatedness Experience . *TEI '11: Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. Funchal, Portugal.
- Ullman, D., Wood, S., & Craig, D. (1990). The Importance of Drawing in the Mechanical Design Process. *Computers & Graphics* , 2, 263-274.
- Valenza, C. & Adkins, J. (2009). Understanding Visual Thinking: The History and Future of Graphic Facilitation. *ACM Interactions*, July + August, 39-45.
- Xiao, X., & Ishii, H. (2011). MirrorFugue: Communicating Hand Gesture in Remote Piano Collaboration . *TEI '11: Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. Funchal, Portugal.
- Yun, R., & Gross, M. (2011). The RayMatic: a Thermostat with a Human Face. *TEI '11: Proceedings of the fifth international conference on Tangible, embedded, and embodied interaction*. Funchal, Portugal.